

Synthesis and characterization of highly water-soluble di-functional β -cyclodextrin monomers

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Abstract : Highly water-soluble di-functional β -cyclodextrin monomers, including 6-diamino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin and 6-diisothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin, have been synthesized. β -Cyclodextrin was first transformed into heptakis 6-deoxy-6-iodo and subsequently to heptakis 6-amino-6-deoxy derivative. Thus 6-diamino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin and 6-diisothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin were prepared in an efficient route for the introduction of more reactive group on smaller rim of β -cyclodextrin without protection of primary and secondary hydroxyl groups. Cyclodextrin was end-capped with disulphonylchloride followed by nucleophilic substitution with sodium azide and subsequently reduced to an amine. These water-soluble monomers were characterized by FT-IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectroscopy.

Keywords : β -Cyclodextrin, isothiocyanate.

Cyclic oligomers of amylase are referred to as cycloligoamyloses, cyclomaltooligosaccharides or cyclodextrins (α -, β -, γ - and δ -cyclodextrin)¹. They have been widely investigated for their ability to form inclusion complexes by inclusion of a wide variety of organic molecules in to their hydrophobic cavity^{2,3}. These cyclomaltooligosaccharides can be used for solubilization, stabilization and targeting of drugs, and has led to the preparation of a wide range of modified CDs⁴. Selective chemical modification of the hydroxyl groups so as to influence the complexation properties and attachment of reactive functional groups for further reaction, is an area of intense research activity⁵. Selective and efficient modification, especially polysubstitutions is complicated by the presence of large number of hydroxyl groups⁶. Among the three -OH groups in a glucopyranose unit, the primary -OH on C₆ has the greatest reactivity, especially when bulky substitution reagents are used, and the secondary -OH on C₃ has the least reactivity. This has been attributed to the hydrogen bonds formed between the protons of the hydroxyl group on C₃ and the oxygen atoms of hydroxyl groups on C₂⁷. The -OH groups on C₃ can only react after all the primary and secondary hydroxyl groups are protected. The functional groups used in the modifications of cyclodextrins are alkyl-, hydroxyalkyl-, carboxyalkyl-, glucosyl-, etc.^{1(a)}. One approach to prepare di-substituted cyclodextrin derivatives with desired

properties is to introduce amino or isothiocyanate groups directly to the primary ring of β -CD instead of protecting the other primary -OH groups in β -CD. The amino or isothiocyanate group is directly attached to the two primary sides of β -CD structure and the anionic -OH group is separated from the ring. Di-amino and di-isothiocyanate β -cyclodextrins have advantages over other β -cyclodextrin derivatives, such as in their reaction to form thiourea linked β -cyclodextrin derivatives or to form chain polymers to reduce the hemolytic effect of CDs⁸. In this communication we report the synthesis of di-amino and di-isothiocyanate β -cyclodextrin by oxido reductive substitution reaction. The key step was the reaction of β -cyclodextrin with biphenyl disulphonyl chloride to form a bisulphonate ester on the smaller rim of β -cyclodextrin. These bisulphonates were reacted with KI/KSCN and sodium azide followed by reduction to form 6-di-amino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin. FT-IR, ^1H NMR and MS analysis was used in the characterization of these β -CD derivatives.

Experimental

Materials and characterization methods :

β -Cyclodextrin was provided by M/s Sigmanet Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai as a gift sample. Biphenyl, KSCN and HSO_3Cl were purchased from National Chemicals (Baroda, India). KI, pyridine, NaN_3 , DMF and acetone

were purchased from E. Merck (India). All other chemicals were purchased from local sources. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer at 30 scans by using a KBr pellet method. ¹H spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer operating at 300 MHz at room temperature. Samples were prepared in DMSO containing TMS as an internal chemical shift standard. Mass spectra were recorded from LC-MS using DMSO as a solvent.

Synthesis :

Biphenyl-4,4'-biphenyl disulphonylchloride : This was prepared by previously known method and characterized. Yield 62.3% (16 g), m.p. 198 °C (reported value : 195–202 °C); FT-IR : 1176 (strong band due to SO₂), 819 cm⁻¹ (*para*-substituted benzene).

Biphenyl-4,4'-disulphonyl capped β-cyclodextrin (1) : A solution of β-CD (4.00 g, 0.00352 mol) in 200 ml dry pyridine was heated at 50 °C under nitrogen atmosphere while 1.120 g (0.0032 mol) of 4,4'-biphenyl disulphonylchloride was added slowly. The mixture was stirred until the solid dissolved completely and then heated at 60 °C for 3 h. The mixture was cooled and pyridine was removed by vacuum distillation and residue was subjected to column chromatography (40% CH₃CN in water). After removing the bulk of CH₃CN on rotary evaporator, the resulting aqueous suspension was lyophilized to dryness. Yield 58.5% (2.85 g); FT-IR : 3400 (hydroxyl), 1176 (strong band due to SO₂), 819 cm⁻¹ (*para*-substituted benzene).

6-Diiodo-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin (2) : A solution of 1 2.0 g (0.00142 mol) in 15 ml DMF and 1.39 g (0.0084 mol) of dry KI was stirred at 80 °C under nitrogen atmosphere for 2 h. After cooling to room temperature the solids were separated by centrifugation and supernatant was decanted. The solid precipitates were washed twice with DMF. Then residue was dissolved in small amount of water and cooled, before acetone was added with rapid stirring. The precipitate was filtered and dried under vacuum. Yield 96.0% (1.93 g); FT-IR : 3400 (hydroxyl stretching), 1157 cm⁻¹ (CH₂I wagging mode).

6-Diazido-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin (3) : A solution of 2 1.704 g (0.00125 mol) in 10 ml DMF and 0.49 g (0.00753 mol) of NaN₃ was stirred at 60 °C under nitrogen atmosphere for 14 h. The solvent was removed and residue dissolved in maximum amount of water. Finally this solution passed through β-zeolite to remove the excess salt. After removing salt the resulting aqueous suspension was freeze-dried to get white solid which was used for the next stage without further purification. Yield 80.9% (1.232 g).

6-Diamino-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin (4) : A solution of 3 1.232 g (0.00104 mol) in 50 ml anhydrous pyridine was added to 0.898 g (0.00342 mol) PPh₃ under stirring for 1 h at room temperature. After that 10 ml concentrated ammonia solution was added and the homogeneous solution stirred for another 14 h. The solvent was removed under vacuum and residue mixed with water and washed twice with benzene to remove the phosphonium oxides. Finally the solution was adjusted to pH 4 by addition of HCl solution. The precipitate was filtered out and aqueous solution was freeze dried to get dry white product. Yield 80.2% (0.92 g); FT-IR : 3400 (-OH stretching hydrogen bonded), 3200 (-NH₂), 2900 (-OH stretching), 2040, 1620, 1490 cm⁻¹ (ammonium combination bands); ¹H NMR (DMSO, 300 MHz) : δ 3.27 (m, 14H-C(6)), 3.48 (t, 7H-C(4)), 3.54 (m, 7H-C(2)), 3.63 (m, 7H-C(3)), 4.82 (m, 5H-C(5)), 4.83 (d, 2H-C(5)), 5.6 (d, 7H-C(1)). MS (C₄₄H₇₄O₃₃N₂).H₂O, 1153 (calcd.), 1153.6 (mass).

6-Diisothiocyanate-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin (5) : A solution of 1 2.0 g (0.00138 mol) in 15 ml DMF and 0.4 g (0.00412 mol) of dry KSCN was stirred at 80 °C under nitrogen atmosphere for 2 h. After cooling to room temperature the solids were separated by centrifugation and supernatant was decanted. The solid precipitates were washed twice with DMF. The residue was dissolved in small amount of water and cooled, before acetone was added with rapid stirring. The precipitate was filtered and dried under vacuum. Yield 60% (0.5 g) FT-IR : 3400, 2061 (C=N), 2341 (X=C=Y cumulated double bond), 1199 cm⁻¹ (C=S); ¹H NMR (DMSO, 300 MHz) : δ 3.27 (m, 14H-C(6)), 3.38 (t, 7H-C(4)), 3.54 (m, 7H-C(2)), 3.66 (m, 7H-C(3)), 4.49 (m, 5H-C(5)), 4.82 (d, 2H-C(5)), 5.60 (d, 7H-C(1)). MS (C₄₄H₆₈O₃₃N₂S₂).2H₂O, 1253 (calcd.), 1252.5 (mass).

Results and discussion

The products denoted 4 and 5 in Fig. 1 were white water-soluble powders. Both the compounds are readily soluble in water. In the IR spectrum for compound 6-diamino-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin peaks at 3400, 3200 cm⁻¹ were observed resulting from the -OH stretching hydrogen bonded and stretching of -NH₂, 2900 (-OH stretching), 2040, 1620, 1490 cm⁻¹ (ammonium combination bands).

The IR spectrum of 6-diisothiocyanate-6-deoxy β-cyclodextrin showed peaks at 3400, 2061 cm⁻¹ due to the -OH stretching and C=N stretching, 2341 cm⁻¹ due to X=C=Y cumulated double bond stretching and 1199 cm⁻¹

Fig. 1. Synthetic procedure for 6-diamino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin (4) and 6-di-isothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin (5).

C=S stretching from -CNS group in 6-di-isothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of 6-diamino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin showed the chemical shifts values of δ 4.82 (m, 5H-C(5)) and 4.83 (d, 2H-C(5)) due to substitution of two -OH groups with -NH₂ groups. In the case of 6-di-isothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin, the ¹H NMR spectra, two protons of C(5) appeared down field at δ 4.82 (d, 2H-C(5)) and other at 4.49 (m, 5H-C(5)) due to disubstitution of two -OH groups with -NCS groups.

The MS spectrum shows that molecular weight of 6-diamino-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin (4) and 6-di-isothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin (5) was 1153.6 and 1252.5 that was similar to that obtained from calculation.

Conclusions :

We have synthesized the 6-diamino-6-deoxy and 6-di-isothiocyanate-6-deoxy β -cyclodextrin monomers. Two primary hydroxyl groups in β -CD were substituted without protection and deprotections steps by oxido-reductive substitution reaction. This synthesis procedure is useful for the synthesis of thiourea linked cyclodextrin polymers.

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